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INGUINAL HERNIA REPAIR BY LICHTENSTEIN TENSION-FREE HERNIOPLASTY TECHNIQUE: TWO YEARS EXPERIENCES.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction; Inguinal hernia repair is one of the most commonly performed surgical procedures in the world. Most surgeons now prefer to perform a tension-free mesh repair. The Lichtenstein tension-free hernioplasty is currently one of the most popular techniques for repair of inguinal hernias.

The aim of this retrospective study was to evaluate the results of inguinal hernia repair using Lichtenstein technique or free mesh tension over a period of two years.

Materials and Methods: Four hundred and twenty-nine patients administered at the University Hospital of Trauma, Tirana, Albania, who underwent inguinal hernia repair with the Lichtenstein-free-tension surgery technique from April 2016 - March 2018, were evaluated retrospectively in relation to demographics, recurrence and postoperative complications. Follow-up data were taken from hospital schedules, recurrence and late complications were assessed in the telephone interview.

Results: In our study, the total number of inguinal hernia patients was 542 patients from these 514 were (94.84%) male and 28 (5.16%) were female. The mean age was 46, 12 years (ranged from 14-92 years). In our study was recorded Inguinal Hernia on the right side in 303 (55.9%) of patients, on the left side in 156 (28.7%) of patients, and 83 (15.4%) of patients had bilateral.

We were recorded 429 (79.3%) patients, who was treated with mesh (according to Lichtenstein) and 113 (20.7%) patients, who was treated without mesh (according to Bassini, Shouldice, Desarda technique).

In our study included 429 patients, their ages ranging from 22 to 92 years with an average age of 45 years, and 381(88.8%) were male and 48(11.2 %) were female with a male-female ratio of 7.9:1. (Tab.1) This gender difference was statistically significant (P = 0.004).

Conclusion: In this study shown that Tension-free hernia repair introduced by Lichtenstein remains the gold standard in open inguinal hernia, it is a common condition among men that increases substantially with aging, medial and lateral hernias both have common and different etiologies.

Risk factors to develop both lateral and medial hernias are older age, and it is a safe and feasible surgery method in respect to 1.8% recurrence and 16.5 % overall post-operative complication rate.

Keywords: Inguinal hernia; Tension-free technique, by Lichtenstein; complications.

INTRODUCTION

Inguinal hernias occur in about 15% of the adult population, and inguinal hernia repair is one of the most common surgical procedures in the world. [1]

Inguinal hernias represent 65%-75% of cases of abdominal wall hernias, with men having 28% and women having 4% lifetime risk of occurrence [2]. Approximately 800,000 mesh hernioplasties are performed each year in the United States, 100,000 in France and 80,000 in the UK. [3]

There are multiple factors involved in inguinal hernia, including pathogens initial incomplete closure of abdominal wall, loss of abdominal wall strength, increased intra-abdominal pressure and changes in the connective tissue [4].

There is morphological and biochemical evidence that adult male inguinal hernias are associated with an altered ratio of type I to type III collagen. [5] These changes lead to weakening of the fibro-connective tissue of the groin and the development of inguinal hernias. [5] Some patients possess characteristics which expose them to a higher risk for postoperative complications and hernia recurrence. Some of these characteristics are older age (>70 years), incisional hernia, previous abdominal surgery and chronic cough [6].

Knowledge of this process led to the acceptance of the need for prosthetic reinforcement of the weakened tissue of the abdominal wall.

Given the evidence that mesh use reduces the recurrence rate, [7, 8] as well as the availability of various prosthetic nets to reinforce the posterior wall of the inguinal canal, most surgeons now prefer to perform a voltage-free repair mesh.

Therefore, this article focuses mainly on Lichtenstein tension-free hernioplasty, which is one of the most popular techniques used to repair inguinal hernia. [9, 10]

Brief theoretical data about types of inguinal hernias; the indirect hernia is defined as a defect that protrudes through the inner or deep inguinal ring; the direct hernia is a defect that protrudes through the posterior wall of the inguinal canal. [2]

To put it in a more anatomical way, an indirect hernia is lateral to the inferior epigastric artery and vein, while a direct hernia is medial to these vessels. The Hesselbach triangle is the area of the inguinal floor through which direct hernias emerge and its boundaries are the lateral

epigastric vessels, the medial rectal sheath, and the inguinal ligament inferiorly. [11]

An incomplete hernia is confined to the inguinal canal, while a complete hernia emerges from the lingual canal through the outer or superficial ring in the scrotum. Direct hernias are always incomplete, while indirect hernias can also be complete. [8]

A sliding inguinal hernia is one in which part of the hernia sac wall consists of an anti-abdominal organ. As the peritoneum stretches and pushes through the hernia defect and becomes the hernia sac, retroperitoneal structures such as the colon or bladder crawl along with it and thus manage to form one of its walls.

Bilateral pediatric hernia are usually indirect hernias and arise due to the openness of the vaginalis process. Just a simple connection of the hernia sac (herniotomy) is enough. Surgical treatment of indirect hernias in adults, unlike that in children, requires more than the simple attachment of the hernia sac. This is because the patent process is only part of the story. Over time, the inner line widens, leaving an adult with what may be a significant defect in the floor of the inguinal canal; this should be closed in addition to splitting or shrinking the indirect hernia sac.

Hydrocele is a pathology commonly encountered in connection with hernias. A communicative hydrocele, by definition, is a form of indirect hernia, albeit with an extremely small defect through which only peritoneal fluid enters the sac but no viscosity exits (e.g., omentum or intestine). [11]

Figure 1 Indirect inguinal hernias develop at the internal inguinal ring and are lateral to the inferior epigastric artery. Direct inguinal hernias occur through Hesselbach's triangle (outlined in blue) formed by the inguinal ligament inferiorly, the inferior epigastric vessels laterally, and the rectus muscle medially. Femoral hernias develop in the

empty space at the medial aspect of the femoral canal, inferior to the inguinal ligament.

Types of hernia repair; Inguinal hernia repairs may be divided into the following three general types: a) Herniotomy (removal of the hernial sac only) - This, by itself, is adequate for an indirect inguinal hernia in children in whom the abdominal wall muscles are normal; formal repair of the posterior wall of the inguinal canal is not required. b) Herniorrhaphy (herniotomy plus repair of the posterior wall of the inguinal canal) - This may be suitable for a small hernia in a young adult with good abdominal wall musculature; the Bassini, Shouldice and Desarda repairs technique are examples of herniorrhaphy. c) Hernioplasty (herniotomy plus reinforcement of the posterior wall of the inguinal canal with a synthetic mesh) - This is required for large hernias and hernias in middle-aged and elderly patients with poor abdominal wall musculature; the Lichtenstein tension-free mesh repair is an example of hernioplasty. [11, 12]

Emphasizing the Halsted principle of no tension, the Lichtenstein group advocated routine use of mesh in 1984. The Lichtenstein tension-free repair has persisted as one of the most commonly performed procedures in the world.

The prosthesis used to reinforce the weakened posterior wall of the inguinal canal is placed between the transversalis fascia and the external oblique aponeurosis and extends well beyond the Hesselbach triangle. Mesh implants do not actively shrink, but they are passively compressed by the natural process of wound healing. Mesh shrinkage occurs only to the extent to which the tissue contracts.

A mesh with a small pore size is likely to shrink more. Shrinkage of the different types of mesh in vivo is in the range of 20-40%; thus, it is important for the surgeon to ensure that the mesh adequately overlaps the defect on all sides. It is advisable to use a large (eg, 7.5 × 15 cm) sheet of mesh extending approximately 2 cm medial to the pubic tubercle, 3-4 cm above the Hesselbach triangle, and 5-6 cm lateral to the internal ring so as to allow for mesh shrinkage.

The Lichtenstein tension-free mesh technique repair, which is an example of hernioplasty and is currently one of the most popular open inguinal hernia repair techniques, includes the following components (steps) (Fig.2):

1) Opening of the subcutaneous fat along the line of the

incision; 2) Opening of the Scarpa fascia down to the external oblique aponeurosis and visualization of the external inguinal ring and the lower border of the inguinal ligament; 3) Opening of the deep fascia of the thigh and exposure of the femoral canal to check for a femoral hernia; 4) Division of the external oblique aponeurosis from the external ring laterally for up to 5 cm, protection the ilioinguinal nerve; 5) Mobilization of the superior (safe guarding the ilio-hypogastric nerve) and inferior flaps of the external oblique aponeurosis to expose the underlying structures; 6) Mobilization of the spermatic cord, along with the cremaster, including the ilioinguinal nerve, the genitofemoral nerve, and the spermatic vessels; all of these structures may then be encircled in a Penrose drain or tape; 7) Opening of the coverings of the spermatic cord and identification and isolation of the hernia sac; 8) Inversion, division, resection, or ligation of the sac, as indicated; 9) Placement and fixation of mesh to the edges of the defect or weakness in the posterior wall of the inguinal canal to create a new artificial internal ring, with care taken to allow some laxity to compensate for increased intra-abdominal pressure when the patient stands; 10) Resection of any nerves that are injured or of doubtful integrity; 11) In males, gentle pulling of the testes back down to their normal scrotal position; 12) Closure of spermatic cord layers, the external oblique aponeurosis, subcutaneous tissue, and the skin. [12, 13]

The surgical mesh is a loosely woven sheet which is used either as a permanent or temporary support for the tissues of the inguinal region during surgery. The surgical mesh is created from both inorganic and biological materials and is used in a variety of operations.

Permanent nets remain in the body, while temporary ones disperse over time. A temporary net was shown in 2012 to be completely dissolved after three years in a scientific trial on sheep. Some types of nets combine permanent and temporary nets, which include both resorbable vicryl, made from polyglycolic acid, and prolene, a non-reusable polypropylene. Another type that is less used in hernia surgery is polyethylene terephthalate which faces complications in the fact that it degrades easily after several years of implantation, erasing the effects of surgery. Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) is also used, but it is produced in the form of a foil and has difficulty integrating into the surrounding tissues, therefore losing stability. [12, 13]

Figure. 2 Tension-free hernia repairs by Lichtenstein

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Four hundred and twenty-nine patients administered at the University Hospital of Trauma, Tirana, Albania, who underwent inguinal hernia repair with the “Lichtenstein-free-tension” technique from April 2016 - March 2018.

In our study all data was assessed retrospectively. To make the study as easy and understandable, the study variables include all the factors that affect the management of the inguinal hernia as; epidemiological factors (age, gender), risk factors (occupation, genetic predisposition, smoker, overweight..), clinic, time of diagnosis, type hernias, size localization, type of anaesthesia, diseases concomitant (diabetes, COPD, cardiovascular diseases...) postoperative stay days, complications, recurrences ...Follow-up data were taken from hospital schedules, recurrence and late complications were assessed in the telephone interview.

After hernioplasty the expected complications were grouped in; Urinary retention, early haemorrhage (within 24 hours) and late (after 24 hours or more), wound and implant infection, scrotal hematoma, testicular atrophy and recurrence of inguinal hernia.

Patients who lose contact after discharge were not included in the study. The Statistical Analysis Social

Science Package (SPSS) 20 for Windows was used in the statistical analysis. The Chi-square test was used to compare qualitative data in addition to descriptive statistical methods (frequency) in evaluating study data. Significance value of $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

In our study, the total number of inguinal hernia patients was 542 patients from these 514 were (94.84%) male and 28 (5.16%) were female. The mean age was 46, 12 years (ranged from 14-92 years). In our study was recorded Inguinal Hernia on the right side in 303 (55.9%) of patients, on the left side in 156 (28.7%) of patients, and 83 (15.4%) of patients had bilateral.

Three hundred and nineteen (58.8%) patients had indirect hernia, and 47 (8.6%) had both indirect and direct types (pantaloon hernia)

We were recorded 429 (79.3%) patients, who was treated with mesh (according to Lichtenstein) and 113 (20.7%) patients, who was treated without mesh (according to Bassini, Shouldice, Desarda technique).

In our study included 429 patients, their ages ranging from 22 to 92 years with an average age of 45 years, and 381(88.8%) were male and 48(11.2 %) were female with a male-female ratio of 7.9:1. (Tab.1) This gender difference was statistically significant ($P = 0.004$).

Table 1 - Distribution of data for Inguinal hernia

Epidemiologic data				
Gender	No	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Male	381	88.8	88.8	88.8
Female	48	11.2	11.2	100.0
Total	429	100.0	100.0	
Localisation of Inguinal hernia				
Left side	91	21.2	21.2	21.2
Right side	308	71.7	71.7	92.9
Bilateral	30	7.1	7.1	100.0
Total	429	100.0	100.0	
Localisation of Inguinal hernia				
Direct	142	33.1	33.1	33.1
Indirect	253	58.9	58.9	92.0
Pantaloon	34	8.0	8.0	100.0
Total	429	100.0	100.0	

Associated Diseases				
COPD	30	6.99	6.99	6.99
Hypertension	39	9.09	9.09	16.08
Diabetes Mellitus	27	6.29	6.29	22.37
Cardiovascular Diseases	28	6.52	6.52	28.9
Total	124	28.9	28.9	
ASA classification				
Class I	231	53.8	53.8	53.8
Class II	111	25.8	25.8	79.6
Class III	71	16.5	16.5	96.1
Class IV	11	2.5	2.5	98.6
Class V	5	1.4	1.4	100.0
Total	429	100.0	100.0	
Sort of Anaesthesia				
Spinal	223	51.9	51.9	51.9
General	121	28.2	28.2	80.1
Local	85	19.9	19.9	100.0
Total	429	100.0	100.0	

The majority of patients 308(71.7%) had right sided inguinal hernia, and 91 (21.2%) had left sided inguinal hernia with a right-to-left ratio of 3.38: 1. Thirty (7.1 %) patients had bilateral inguinal hernias. (Tab.1)

Two hundred and fifty-three (58.9%) of patients had indirect inguinal hernia, 142 (33.1%) of patients had direct inguinal hernia, and 34 (8.0%) had both indirect and direct inguinal hernia (pantaloon hernia) (Tab.1)

In according the risk factors (occupation, genetic predisposition, smoker, overweight...), which are favourable to the occurrence of hernia, we have found those data as follow: a) History of heavy weight lifting (construction worker, unloading load) was found in 159 (37.0%) patients, in 205 (47.7%) patients were smokers, in only 82 (19.1%) patients had more than 1 family member with hernial pathology, in only 69 (16.1%) patients were overweight.

The delivery of comorbidities was as follow; in 124 (28.9%) patients. Of these, 30 (6.99 %) had chronic lung infections, 39 (9.09 %) had hypertension, 27 (6.29 %) had diabetes mellitus, and 28 (6.52%) patients had cardiovascular diseases. (Tab.1)

All of these associated medical conditions were checked before surgery.

According to the ASA classification, 231 (53.8%) of patients had class I ASA; 111 (25.8%) of patients had class II ASA, 71(16.5%) of patients had ASA class III, 11 (2.5%) of patients had ASA class IV, and 5 (1.4 %) of patients had ASA class V. (Tab.1)

Elective hernia surgery was performed in all patients, which was performed under spinal anesthesia in 223 (51.9 %) patients, general anesthesia in 121 (28.2 %) patients and local anesthesia in 85 (19.9 %) patients. Type of anesthesia was determined by the anesthesiologist.

The average hospital stay after surgery was 2.8 days (range 1-7 days). For patients who experienced seroma and hematoma the day hospital stay was 2 and 3 days respectively.

In our study, the overall complication rate was 16.5%.

The most common early postoperative complication was urinary retention which required urinary catheterization in 35 (8.1%) cases; operative wound infection in 12 (2.7%) cases, seroma in 15 (3.5%) cases, hematoma in 5 (1.1%) cases, and scrotal oedema 16 (3.7%). (Tab.2)

Only in two cases we had reintervention for re-evaluation of haemostasis, after giant inguinoscrotal hematomas, in one it was intervened after 8 hours, in the other case after 12 hours.

In 35 cases with urinary retention, they were temporarily catheterized for 24 hours in 24 cases, in 9 cases a urinary catheter was left for 2 weeks (after consultation with the urologist as he had benign prostatic hypertrophy). Infections of the operative wound were treated with washing and drainage and in 4 cases the removal of the mass was decided. (Tab.2)

Late complications including chronic pain in 13 (3.0%) of cases, testicular atrophy in 2 (0.4%) of cases, and recurrence in 8 (1.8%) of cases. (Tab.2)

Eight (1.8%) of patients who developed scrotal oedema were recurrent patients with scrotal hernia, as extensive dissection was necessary.

In the cases with scrotal oedema 16 (3.7%) we have used non-operative therapeutic procedures such as; the use of local anti-inflammatory ointments, and the raising of the testicles with suspending trousers, and their reduction was found within 5-7 days.

No additional intervention was performed in patients with pain, and with symptoms of paraesthesia in the thigh, they were treated symptomatically (paracetamol,

Indomethacin, Lyrica...)

Complication	No	%	Cumulative %
Early Postoperative Complication			
Urinary Retention	35	8.1	8.1
Operative Wound Infection	12	2.7	10.8
Seroma	15	3.5	14.3
Hematoma	5	1.1	15.4
Scrotal Oedema	16	3.7	19.1
Total	83	19.1	
Late Complications			
Testicular Atrophy	2	0.4	0.4
Recurrence	8	1.8	2.2
Chronic Pain	13	3.0	5.2
Total	23	5.2	

Table 2 - Distribution of Complication after Hernioplasty by Lichtenstein

DISCUSSION

Our study shows that the inguinal hernia repair technique, like Lichtenstein's tension-free graft technique, is a reliable and successful method, already confirmed by other studies that we will present below, should be based on some basic elements of evaluation of an operating technique related to; patient's hospital stays, postoperative complications both early and late, and by recurrence rate.

Based on the data of our study, 429 patients were registered, out of which 381 (88.8%) of cases was male and 48 (11.2%) of cases were female, with a male-female ratio of 7.9:1, which is in full harmony with the literature data, Burcharth et al. shown inguinal hernia can occurs in both genders, but mainly affects men [4], also Jenkins et al. have reported that 65%-75% of cases of abdominal wall hernias, with men having 28% and women having 4% lifetime risk of occurrence [2].

Lee et al. reported as for age as a risk factor, we demonstrated that the rate of inguinal hernia repair increases with age in male patients, which may be related to increasing muscular weakness with age.[23]

In our study the hernia was detected on the right side in 308 (71.7%) and on the left side in 91 (21.2%), and the bilateral hernia was detected in 30 (7.1%). Indirect hernia was detected in 253 (58.9%), direct hernia was detected in 142 (33.1%), pantaloon hernia was detected in 34 (8.0 %).

Pielaci ski et al. have been reported to be detected mainly on the right side in previous studies, and 60-65% of all hernias were indirect and 30-35% were direct hernias [16]. Kingsnorth et al. reported in their 2003 review with 476 patients that 439 were inguinal hernias, and the rate of direct / indirect hernias was reported as 13 times. [17]

In our study only 82 (19.1%) patients had more than 1 family member with hernial pathology, also Burcharth and Pedersen in a nationwide study found that groin hernias are clustered in families, which was most prominent for daughters to mothers that had undergone groin hernia surgery .[18] Mihailov et al found that Family specific mutations have been identified in a family with lateral and medial hernias through several generations.[19]

Lou et al. reported that in cases with the family history of inguinal hernia, the probability of developing inguinal hernia is approximately 8 times higher.[20]

In according the obesity in our study only 69 (16.1%) patients were overweight, likewise Chan Yong Park et al. have reported that in adult inguinal hernia, it is developed at relatively younger ages in overweight and obese patients in comparison with normal weight patients, and the rate of elderly patients aged 60 or more is 47.1% in overweight and obese patients, and it is less than 60.0% of normal weight patients.[21]

In rendering the risk factors which are favourable to the occurrence of hernia, we have found those data as follow: a) History of heavy weight lifting (construction worker, unloading load) was found in 159 (37.0%) patients, in 205 (47.7%) patients were smokers, in only 82 (19.1%) patients had more than 1 family member with hernial pathology, in only 69 (16.1%) patients were overweight. Similarly, Sanjay and Lou et al. reported that in patient that repeated lifting heavy materials for a long period or activities requiring a big force suddenly, chronic cough, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, education levels, drinking, monthly net income, etc. have been reported to be risk factors. [20, 22]

The delivery of comorbidities in our study was as follow; in 124 (28.9%) patients. Of these, 30 (6.99 %) had chronic lung infections, 39 (9.09 %) had hypertension, 27 (6.29 %) had diabetes mellitus, and 28 (6.52%) patients had cardiovascular diseases. (Tab.1)

Clark et al. Based on their results, founded the direct hernia is a risk factor in men and it may indicate greater abdominal wall weakness if patients develop a direct hernia and explain why patients with a direct hernia have

a higher risk because of their comorbidities as prostate disease, severe liver disease, and cirrhosis, COPD, Diabetes, CV diseases... these conditions had a higher risk because of increased abdominal pressure.[24]

Elective hernia surgery was performed in all patients, which was performed under spinal anesthesia in 223 (51.9 %) patients, general anesthesia in 121 (28.2 %) patients and local anesthesia in 85 (19.9 %) patients. Type of anesthesia was determined by the anesthesiologist.

Fitzgibbons et al. reported that people can be administered by local anesthesia, a spinal block, and general anesthesia. [10] Nordin et al. also reported that local anesthesia has been shown to cause less postoperative pain, shorten surgery time, shorten recovery time and reduce the need to return to hospital. [25] Van Veen et al. also reported people undergoing general anesthesia tend to be able to go home faster and experience fewer complications. [26] The European Society of Hernia recommends the use of local anesthesia especially for people with a persistent medical condition. [27, 28]

The average hospital stay after surgery in our study was 2.8 days (range 1-7 days). For patients who experienced seroma and hematoma the day hospital stay was 2 and 3 days respectively.

Aldoescu et al. reported that the surgical treatment of inguinal hernia needs short duration hospital stays, the post-operative complications but also the other factors that depend on the patient, can affect the post-operative course.[29]

In our study, the overall complication rate was 16.5%, and in according the Simons MP, Aufenacker T, Bay-Nielsen M, and et al. the overall risk of complications after inguinal hernia operations 15 to 28% in systematic reviews [30].

The most common early postoperative complication in our study was urinary retention which required urinary catheterization in 35 (8.1%) cases; operative wound infection in 12 (2.7%) cases, seroma in 15 (3.5%) cases, hematoma in 5 (1.1%) cases, and scrotal oedema 16 (3.7%). (Tab.2). The late complications including chronic pain in 13 (3.0%) of cases, testicular atrophy in 2 (0.4%) of cases, and recurrence in 8 (1.8%) of cases.

Forte et al. in their study with 875 patients reported, the complications observed were: urine retention (1.6%), superficial haematoma (1.3%), superficial infection (1%), wound suppuration (0.5%), serous effusion (0.7%), postsurgery pain (2.1%), scrotal edema (1.7%), persistent

inguinal neuralgia (0.6), local hypoesthesia (4.3%), ischemical orchitis (0.1%), recurrence (0.2%).[31]

Shamberger et al. reported vascular injury is a less common but reported and potentially disastrous pitfall. It can be avoided by respecting the proximity of the femoral vessels, particularly when the mesh is being sutured to the inguinal ligament. Hematoma formation can be due either to injury of the inferior epigastric vessels or to failure to ligate the superficial subcutaneous veins. [32]

Sanchez-Manuel et al. also shown as in all operations, infection is a concern, but in clinical settings where the rate of wound infection is low (<5%), there is no indication for the routine use of antibiotic prophylaxis in low-risk patients. [33, 34]

Hair A, Duffy K, McLean J, Taylor S, Smith H, Walker A, et al. founded that, in a large Swedish study found that 30% of postherniorrhaphy patients reported long-term pain or discomfort, 6% of whom experienced pain intense enough to alter their activities of daily living. [38]

Although pain is more common in the acute postoperative period, it remains chronically severe in 3% of patients reported O'Dwyer et al., having significant effects on their work and social activities. [39]

Gopal et al. reported another phenomenon that can be experienced after hernia repair is groin numbness, and in a large Scottish study that included more than 5500 patients, this was reported to various pain degrees in as many as 9%.[36]

Nilsson et al. reported other complications include seroma formation, bruising and hematoma (7% of cases), and wound infection (1-7% of cases).[40]

Arslani shown that ischemic orchitis leading to testicular atrophy or even necrosis is a catastrophic but well-known complication of inguinal hernia repair.[37] Taylor et al. shown that symptoms include painful testicular swelling and fever commencing 2-3 days after surgery. The exact cause of this rare complication is unclear, but it is thought to be secondary to venous thrombosis rather than arterial injury. A high index of suspicion for postoperative ischemic orchitis, in conjunction with emergency testicular ultrasonography, may help avoid orchiectomy. [41]

CONCLUSIONS

In this study shown that Tension-free hernia repair

introduced by Lichtenstein remains the gold standard in open inguinal hernia, it is a common condition among men that increases substantially

with aging, medial and lateral hernias both have common and different etiologies.

Risk factors to develop both lateral and medial hernias are older age, and it is a safe and feasible surgery method in respect to 1.8% recurrence and 16.5 % overall post-operative complication rate.

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Authorship Contribution; The first author has done the conception or design of the work and data collection and analysis. The second author has done the data analysis and interpretation as well as drafting the article and critical revision of the article. The third author did the English writing of the work, the collection, the data control, the English writing of the Article.

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